

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R9.4 Project graphic style package

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December 2020

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1 INTRODUCTION (TITLE 1, 18 P)

In order to support the presentations and publication efforts of the project, CGS in cooperation with project partners prepared a project graphic style package (result R9.4). Graphic style package contains the project logo (including a manual for its use), a PowerPoint presentation template, Word presentation template and background for online meetings and conferences. The created graphic style will be further used for the preparation of other outputs like poster template, report cover sheet, etc. Project graphic style follows the rules set in the Communication and Design Manual of EEA and Norway Grants 2014-2021.

2 PROJECT GRAPHIC STYLE PACKAGE

2.1 Project logo

2.1.1 Design manual – CZ version

PROJEKT CO2 SPICER / GRAFICKÝ MANUÁL LOGOTYP / ZÁKLADNÍ BAREVNOST

LOGOTYP / OCHRANNÁ ZÓNA LOGOTYP / DOPORUČENÁ A MINIMÁLNÍ VELIKOST

2.1.2 Design manual – EN version

CO2SPICER PROJECT / DESIGN MANUAL LOGOTYPE / COLOUR PALETTE VALUES

LOGOTYPE / BUFFER ZONE LOGOTYPE / RECOMMENDED AND MINIMUM SIZE

2.2 PowerPoint presentation templates

2.2.1 PowerPoint presentation template 4x3 – CZ version

2.2.2 PowerPoint presentation template 16x9 – CZ version

2.2.3 PowerPoint presentation template 4x3 – EN version

2.2.4 PowerPoint presentation template 16x9 – EN version

NAZEV DOKUMENTU STATA TYPYKAPA PATA

CO₂ SPICER

3 Nadpis 1, 18 b

3.1 Nadpis 2, 16 b

Text bez dělení 12 b, řádkování 19 b, mezera za 6 b

Obt. 3-1. Vycentrovaný, popisek text 11 b. Foto X. Zdroj: X.

Text bez dělení 12 b, řádkování 19 b, mezera za 6 b

Tab. 3-1: Popisek text 11 b

Y	X	Z	S	S	X
0	B	K	1989		
1	L	H	1992		
2	T	K	1989		
3	L	H	1991		

5

NAZEV DOKUMENTU STATA TYPYKAPA PATA

CO₂ SPICER

Text bez dělení 12 b, řádkování 19 b, mezera za 6 b

Obt. 3-2. Na celou šířku textu, popisek text 11 b. Foto X. Zdroj: X.

3.1.1 Nadpis 3, 15 b

Text bez dělení 12 b, řádkování 19 b, mezera za 6 b

6

NAZEV DOKUMENTU STATA TYPYKAPA PATA

CO₂ SPICER

Text bez dělení 12 b, řádkování 19 h, mezera za 6 b

LITERATURA

Příklady citací:

Články v časopisech:

Alekin, O. A. (1962): Grundlagen der Wasserchemie. –260 str. Dtsch. Verlag Grundstoffind. Leipzig.

Aydin, A., Smith, J. (1978): Small faults formed as deformation bands in sandstone. – Pure appl. Geophys. 114, 913–930.

Čilek, V., Horáček, P., Novák, J. (2010): Saxon-Bohemian Switzerland. In: Mizon, P., ed.: Geomorphological Landscapes of the World. 201–209. –Springer.

Články v elektronických časopisech:

Gnoll, M. (2003): Northern Gondwanan Siluro-Devonian palaeogeography assessed by cephalopods. – Palaeont. Electron. 5(2), <http://palaeo-electronica.org>, 1–19.

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NAZEV DOKUMENTU STATA TYPYKAPA PATA

CO₂ SPICER

Tento výstup byl připraven v rámci projektu CO2-SPICER.

Projekt CO2-SPICER je podpořen grantem Norska a Technologické agentury České republiky ve výši 2,32 mil. €

Více informací o projektu naleznete na co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PARTNEŘI PROJEKTU

8

NAME DOCUMENT AVYTA VYTVYATA TAVT

CO₂ SPICER

3 Title 1, 18 b
3.1 Title 2, 16 b

Text without division 12 b, spacing 19 b, space after 6 b

Fig. 3-1: Centered, label text 11 b. Photo Xxxxxxxx. Source: Xxxxxxxx.

Text without division 12 b, spacing 19 b, space after 6 b

Tab. 3-4: Label text 11 b

0	XXXXXX	XXXXXX	1989	XXXXXX	XXXXXX
1	XXXXXX	XXXXXX	1992	XXXXXX	XXXXXX
2	XXXXXX	XXXXXX	1989	XXXXXX	XXXXXX
3	XXXXXX	XXXXXX	1991	XXXXXX	XXXXXX

5

NAME DOCUMENT AVYTA VYTVYATA TAVT

CO₂ SPICER

Text without division 12 b, spacing 19 b, space after 6 b

Fig. 3-2: Full width text, label text 11 b. Photo Xxxxxxxx. Source: Xxxxxxxx.

3.1.1 Title 3, 16 b

Text without division 12 b, spacing 19 b, space after 6 b

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NAME DOCUMENT AVYTA VYTVYATA TAVT

CO₂ SPICER

Text without division 12 b, spacing 19 b, space after 6 b

REFERENCES

Examples of references:

Journal articles

Alekin, O. A. (1962): Grundlagen der Wasserchemie. –269 str. Dtsch. Verlag Grundstoffind. Leipzig.

Aydin, A., Smith, J. (1978): Small faults formed as deformation bands in sandstone. – Pure appl. Geophys. 116, 913–930.

Cilek, V., Horacek, P., Novak, J. (2010): Saxon-Bohemian Switzerland. In: Migon, P., ed.: Geomorphological Landscapes of the World. 201–209. –Springer.

Elektronic journal articles

Gnoli, M. (2003): Northern Gondwanan Siluro-Devonian palaeogeography: assessed by cephalopods. – Palaeont. Electron. 5(2), <http://palaeo-electronica.org>, 1–19.

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NAME DOCUMENT AVYTA VYTVYATA TAVT

CO₂ SPICER

This deliverable/result was prepared as a part of the CO2-SPICER project

The CO2-SPICER project benefits from a € 2.32 mill. Grant from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at co2-spicer.geology.cz

PROJECT PARTNERS

 Programme **Kappa**

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2.4 Background for online meetings and conferences

Programme **Kappa**

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This report is a result of the CO2-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO2-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

Programme **Kappa**

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